

MERGER BOON OR BANE – AN ANALYSIS OF BANK OF BARODA PRE & POST-MERGER FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE USING A CAMEL APPROACH

Dr. Pawan Kumar, Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Delhi College of Arts and Commerce, University of Delhi

Mr. Akash Yadav, Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, National PG College, Lucknow

Mr. Rahul Yadav, Research Scholar, School of Education, Central University of Haryana

ABSTRACT

Purpose – This research aims at the Bank of Baroda's financial performance analysis pre-merger and post-merger with Vijaya Bank and Dena Bank. The performance evaluation of the banking industry is a helpful criterion and diagnostic in assessing the overall consistency of the economic growth of a country.

Design/methodology/approach – The CAMEL model was used to assess the bank's financial strength pre-merger and post-merger. The data for the study was collected from the Annual reports published by the bank from 2016-17 to 2021-22.

Findings – The findings of the study indicate that the merger doesn't have any significant effect on the financial performance of Bank of Baroda. Post-merger Capital adequacy and asset quality are improved, and NPA's of the bank declined which is a good indicator of its overall profitability. Post-merger Liquidity of the bank decreased as LATD & LATA ratio showed a declining trend. BOB is able to keep its Credit Deposit Ratio above the 60% banking sector national average. The realization of post-merger synergies and the broad-based economic recovery made FY21-22 a standout year for the bank, which resulted in higher business growth and profitability.

KEYWORDS :CAMEL, Capital Adequacy, Asset Quality, Management, Earning, Liquidity, Merger

INTRODUCTION

Banks are the backbone of economic growth in any country because they are the primary source of credit creation for companies, MSMEs, and the general public and also perform the function of accepting deposits and providing general utility and agency services. For socioeconomic development, the country requires a responsive financial sector that assists households, companies, and MSMEs in meeting their economic, financial & social needs. (Banking Sector in India, 2022) There are 12 public sector banks, 22 private sector banks, 46 foreign banks, 56 regional rural banks, 1485 urban cooperative banks, and 96,000 rural cooperative banks in India's banking system as of September 2021. The banking system is an essential component of any economy and plays a critical role in its overall economic development and growth. There is a significant link between economic expansion and the growth of the financial sector.

(Kumar & Malhotra, 2017) A bank's financial position and performance evaluation are important for depositors, stockholders, employees, and the entire economic development of the country. Even though it ascertains a bank's competitiveness in the market and plays an important role in the economy's overall growth. (Sayed & Sayed, 2013) The Indian banking sector is among the fastest expanding banking sector in the world, and it has been operating in a somewhat more competitive and international environment since liberalization. As a result, sound financial position and oversight have become a need. (Swami, Nethaji, & Sharma, 2019) The third pillar requires the bank to uphold very strong standards for public disclosure of information about its actual capital, risk profile, risk management systems, and regulatory control. The stakeholders would be able to gauge the strain and financial health of the bank using this pillar of the financial system. (Kaur, 2010) Due to globalization in the worldwide market, the Indian banking industry has seen significant changes in recent years, resulting in strong rivalry. (Roman & Sargu, 2013) The banking sector must be analysed and appraised

to enable the seamless rehabilitation and elimination of possible risks to provide a healthy, solid, and stable banking industry. Thus, one of the most well-liked techniques for analysing and rating the soundness of the bank is the CAMEL model.

(Poddar, 2019) Mergers are when two businesses come together to become one. The general premise of a MERGER is that two independent businesses working together will produce more value than either of them working alone. Companies continue to assess various opportunities via the merger or acquisition route with the primary goal of wealth maximization. (Ojha, 2020) The merger of Vijaya Bank and Dena Bank with Bank of Baroda took place on April 1, 2019. Post-merger, Bank of Baroda thus became the 3rd largest bank and the 2nd largest public sector bank followed by State bank of India.

OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

1. To analyse the pre and post-merger performance of the Bank of Baroda.
2. To identify the impact of the merger on the financial position of the Bank of Baroda.
3. To identify the significant changes in its Capital Adequacy, Asset Quality, Management Efficiency, Earnings, and Liquidity post-merger.

HYPOTHESIS

The following null hypothesis has been framed for study:

H01: There is no significant impact of the merger on the Capital Adequacy of Bank of Baroda.

H02: There is no significant impact of the merger on the Assets Quality of Bank of Baroda.

H03: There is no significant impact of the merger on the Management efficiency of Bank of Baroda.

H04: There is no significant impact of the merger on the Earnings of Bank of Baroda.

H05: There is no significant impact of the merger on the Liquidity of the Bank of Baroda.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

(Yildirim & Ildokuz, 2020) Due to the fierce competition, earnings are crucial output for the continuation of operations and sustained growth of banks. The findings of this study indicate that the ROA and ROE ratios of banks are significantly influenced by capital, management, and liquidity status. However, the above-mentioned ratios are not significantly impacted by asset quality or sensitivity to market risks.

(Singh & Milan, 2020) It has been discovered that asset quality is negatively linked to public-sector bank performance. The performance of India's public sector banks is inversely linked to liquidity and inflation. Capital adequacy is positively related to bank performance but negatively related to interest margin. GDP growth has a considerable positive relationship with bank performance but has an inverse relationship with interest income.

(Swami, Nethaji, & Sharma, 2019) Banks with relatively low levels of capital, lower levels of profitability, a less diversified portfolio, poor operating and managerial efficiency, and higher levels of non-performing assets (NPAs) are all associated with a higher risk of having deteriorated asset quality. In general, empirical analysis suggests that the Regulatory and Supervisory Department of the Central Bank may consider a relatively low level of capital, declining profitability, and poor operational efficiency as good predictors to recognize the bank whose asset quality is likely to deteriorate well in advance.

(Risal & Panta, 2019) The study concludes that risk management and supervision have a significant relation based on the findings. This finding demonstrates the central bank's commendable efforts in risk management and banking supervision. The study's findings indicate that one of the most crucial elements in reducing the risk faced by Nepal's commercial banks is the quality of their assets. By lowering NPL, maintaining adequate liquidity, and improving management effectiveness, commercial banks in Nepal can lower their downside deviation as well as the standard deviation of ROA and ROE.

(Patel, 2018) Their study aimed to determine the comparative long-term profitability position of the selected Indian bank's pre-merger and post-merger. To test the hypothesis, he used a descriptive

research design, a basic research approach, and a paired t-test. He concluded that the merger has a negative relationship with return on equity, return on assets, net profit ratio, the yield on advance, and the yield on investment. However, earnings per share, profit per employee, and business per employee have all increased since the merger.

(Sharma & Arora, 2016) The growth of a country's banking industry has a significant impact on its economic growth. This study used the CAMEL model to analyse the long-term term viability of a sample of 15 banks operating in India during the 2014-15 financial year. According to the survey, private banks are in a stronger position and have outperformed public sector banks. In respect of asset quality and management productivity, there is scope for improvement in public sector banks.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To make a comparative analysis of pre and post-merger performance the data for this study is gathered from the Bank of Baroda's annual reports from the period 2016-17 to 2021-22 and the CAMEL model is used to analyse results. CAMEL model is a ratio-based approach that was invented in the 1970s - 1980s by (Kiran, 2018) 3 federal banking regulators in the United States (the Federal Reserve, the FDIC, and the OCC) as a consistent supervisory evaluation system. The CAMEL model assesses a banking institution's overall performance by calculating numerous financial ratios from the financial reports disclosed by banks

ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

CAPITAL ADEQUACY

The term "capital adequacy" refers to a bank's ability to absorb unforeseen events. (Yildirim & Ildokuz, 2020) A key tool for determining the ideal level of capital that a bank should have in case of unforeseen risks and uncertainties is capital adequacy. (Sharma & Arora, 2016) Capital Adequacy is the minimum needed amount that a bank must hold as a reserve for its depositors and stockholders.

It includes the following ratios –

1. Capital Adequacy Ratio

Based on the worth of the bank's assets, the capital necessary to manage risk is determined by the capital adequacy ratio. (Sayed & Sayed, 2013) RBI requires for both credit and market risk; banks must maintain a minimum Capital Risk-weighted Assets Ratio (CRAR) of 9%. (Agarwala & Agarwala, 2019) Additionally, it is preferred that financial institutions maintain a certain level of capital adequacy to boost their net worth.

Table II – Analysis of Capital Adequacy Ratio - Bank of Baroda

Pre – Merger					Post – Merger				
Year	CAR	CET I	TIER I	TIER II	Year	CAR	CET I	TIER I	TIER II
2016-17	12.24	8.98	9.93	2.31	2019 – 20	13.30	9.44	10.71	2.59
2017-18	12.13	9.23	10.46	1.67	2020 – 21	14.99	10.94	12.67	2.32
2018-19	13.42	10.38	11.55	1.87	2021 – 22	15.98	11.59	13.34	2.50
Mean	12.59	9.53	10.65	1.95	Mean	14.75	10.66	12.24	2.47

Source: Authors' Calculation

Table II shows that BOB is able to maintain CAR > 9% prescribed by the RBI for risk-weighted assets and also it shows an upward trend after the merger. As per results, the Bank of Baroda witnessed a decrease in Capital adequacy ratio in the next year after the merger as CAR decreased by .12, but it shows an upsurge in the upcoming years as CAR witnessed an average increase of 2.16 % which is a good sign (Rizvi et al., 2018) as high capital adequacy ratio enhances the earnings of the banks.

2. Advances to Total Assets

The ratio of advances to total assets indicates how aggressively a bank lends. (Sayed & Sayed, 2013) It is preferable to have a higher ratio of advances to total assets. As lending is the key operation of the bank and the earnings of the banks depend upon it. A higher ATA ratio is preferred as a high proportion of advances over total assets results in higher earnings which leads to increased profitability.

3. Debt-Equity Ratio

The debt-equity ratio displays the proportion of debt to shareholders' funds. (Gandhi, Chhajer, & Mehta, 2020) The lower the ratio, the greater the capital adequacy. According to the ideal debt-to-equity ratio of 2:1, borrowing should never be more than twice as a shareholder's fund because doing so increases risk.

Table III – Analysis of ATA & Debt Equity Ratio - Bank of Baroda

Pre – Merger			Post – Merger		
	ATA (%)	Debt–Equity		ATA (%)	Debt–Equity Ratio
2016-17	55.15	0.7595	2019 – 20	59.60	1.2952
2017-18	59.37	1.4419	2020 – 21	61.13	0.8676
2018-19	60.09	1.4627	2021 – 22	60.81	1.2092
Mean	58.20	1.22	Mean	60.51	1.12

Source: Authors' Calculation

Table III shows that advances to total assets ratio also witnesses a decline of .49% in the next year after the merger, but later on years it showed an increasing trend. (Swami et al., 2019) A financial crisis could occur if the decline in bank asset quality is not carefully addressed because it indicates flaws in the banking system.

Table III shows that a Merger has a positive effect on the Debt equity ratio as it shows a downward trend of .10. Decrease in the debt-equity ratio is preferable as a higher DER is an indicator of high risk as borrowings are the fixed burden for the company which decreases the overall profit available to shareholders.

Table IV – Paired T-test Pre & Post Merger of Capital Adequacy - Bank of Baroda

Ratios	Merger	Mean	S.D.	DF	T – Value	P – Value	Difference
CAR	Pre	12.59	.715	2	3.879	0.06	No Significant Difference
	Post	14.75	1.355				
ATA	Pre	58.20	2.668	2	2.079	.173	No Significant Difference
	Post	60.51	.806				
DER	Pre	1.22	.400	2	-.295	.796	No Significant Difference
	Post	1.12	.226				

According to the results of paired t-test, capital adequacy has a T-value of 3.879 and a P-value of 0.06, Advances to Total Assets have a T-value of 2.079 and a P-value of 0.173, and Debt Equity Ratio has a T-value of -.295 and a P-value of 0.796. As per the findings of paired T-test the significance value is greater than the 0.05 level for the CAR, ATA & DE ratio, indicating that the Merger doesn't have a significant impact on the capital adequacy of Bank of Baroda. Overall results indicate that the Bank of Baroda doesn't witness a significant change in its overall capital adequacy as a result of the merger.

ASSET QUALITY

The extent of financial strength and risk in assets, primarily loans and investments, is usually referred to as asset quality. (Kaur, 2010) All aspects of the profitability of the banks are determined by the quality of their assets to different variables. (Gaur & Mohapatra, 2020) Specifically, the Indian economy has witnessed an increase in non-performing assets (NPAs) in the banking sector during the past few years. Liquidity is significant because the assets' value is highly risky and prone to volatility. It includes the following ratios –

1. Gross Non-Performing Assets to Gross Advances

The quality of assets is an important measure of a bank's strength, to determine the percentage of non-performing assets to advances. (Agarwala & Agarwala, 2019) Banks primarily rely on interest from advances and loans as well as principal repayment for their income. Such assets are categorized as non-performing assets if they fail to produce income.

2. Net Non-Performing Assets to Net Advance

NPAs are the primary metrics used to evaluate the efficiency of the banks. The lower the NPA the better the financial position of the bank, as non-performing assets are loss assets resulting decrease in the profitability of banks. (Ramu, 2009) The ratios of net NPA to net advance are used to assess the severity of the bank's NPA problem.

3. Total Investment to Total Assets

TITA indicates the proportion of total assets banks has invested in different securities to safeguard against NPAs. (Gandhi, Chhajer, & Mehta, 2020) To protect against NPAs, a higher amount is kept in investments, as indicated by a higher TITA ratio.

Table V – Ratio Analysis of Asset Quality - Bank of Baroda

Source: Authors Calculation

Pre – Merger				Post – Merger			
Year	GNPA (%)	NNPA (%)	TITA (%)	Year	GNPA (%)	NNPA (%)	TITA (%)
2016-17	10.46	4.72	18.65	2019 – 20	9.4	3.13	23.71
2017-18	12.26	5.49	22.66	2020 – 21	8.87	3.09	22.60
2018-19	9.61	3.33	23.34	2021 – 22	6.61	1.72	24.71
Mean	10.77	4.51	21.55	Mean	8.29	2.64	23.67

Table V shows that the merger is beneficial for the bank as its Gross NPA showed a decreasing trend after the merger which is a good indicator of the bank's overall profitability as NPA's are the loss assets which result in a decrease in the earnings of the bank. After the merger gross NPA to gross advances shows an average decrease of 2.48 bps from 10.77% as of the pre-merger average to 8.29% as of the post-merger average. (V., 2007) Lower GNPA acts as a testing instrument which reflects the ability of the management in discovering and absorbing the risk of NPAs. After the merger, the Net NPA of the bank showed a continuous decline, which is a sound indicator of improved asset quality. After the merger NNPA shows an average decline of 1.84 bps from 4.51% as of the pre-merger average to 2.64% as of the post-merger average. (Albulescu, 2015) A significant amount of NPAs harms the profitability of the banking industry. This decline indicates that the Bank of Baroda is paying special attention on loan collection to make sure that the increment was long-lasting and that overdue and non-performing assets lending was handled promptly. The results also indicate that there is a positive sign of a merger on TITA as it witnessed an upsurge. After the merger, TITA increased by an average of 2.12% which is a good sign as more amount from total assets is invested by the bank to safeguard from the NPAs and to improve the asset quality.

Table VI – Paired T-test Pre & Post Merger of Asset Quality - Bank of Baroda

Ratios	Merger	Mean	S.D.	DF	T – Value	P – Value	Differences Pre & Post Merger
GNPA	Pre	10.77	1.353	2	3.447	0.075	No Significant Difference
	Post	8.29	1.481				
NNPA	Pre	4.51	1.094	2	6.998	.020	Significant Difference
	Post	2.64	.802				
TITA	Pre	21.55	2.534	2	-1.392	.298	No Significant Difference
	Post	23.67	1.055				

As per the findings of paired t-test, GNPA has a T-value of 3.447 and a P-value of 0.075, NNPA has a T-value of 6.998 and a P-value of 0.020, and TITA has a T-value of -1.392 and a P-value of 0.298. As per the results of paired T-test, the significance value is greater than the 0.05 level for the GNPA & TITA ratio, indicating that the Merger doesn't have a significant impact on the Gross NPA's and Total Investment to Total assets of Bank of Baroda. Overall results indicate that the Bank of Baroda doesn't witness a significant change in its overall Asset Quality as a result of the merger.

MANAGEMENT EFFICIENCY

For the purpose of gauging management effectiveness, it uses an arbitrary analysis. (Sakarya, 2020) The management of the bank not only identifies, quantifies, supervises, and regulates operational risks but also makes sure that all bank operations are efficient and compliant with both internal and external laws and regulations.

1. Business Per Employee

BPE indicates that business is generated from core operations of deposits and advances per number of employees. It is calculated by dividing the total number of employees by the sum of the core deposits and net advances. (Evans, Leone, & Hilbers, 2000) Overstaffing can lead to inefficiencies and low or declining business per employee, which can have an equivalent impact on profits.

2. Profit Per Employee

This displays the per-employee surplus. (Singh & Singh, 2015) The result is calculated by dividing the bank's profit after tax by the existing staff. (Graham, 2019) Profit per employee, or what I refer to as "return on people," is one of the most commonly ignored performance metrics. (Swami et al., 2019) Under the CAMEL model, profit per employee is a crucial indicator of how well the banks are managing their operations.

3. Return on Equity

A measure of a net income as a percentage of its shareholders' equity. (Albulescu, 2015) By revealing how much profit was earned with the funds shareholders invested, return on equity serves as a gauge of the banking industry's profitability. The ROE reveals how effectively the management is at returning the capital that its shareholders invested in it. (Bauman, 2014) ROE is probably the most important key measure as it gives the firm exposure to the net profit that was left to it along with the value of its own capital, or the proportion of all shareholders' capital that the company owns.

Pre – Merger				Post – Merger			
Year	BPE (Crore)	PPE (Crore)	ROE (%)	Year	BPE (Crore)	PPE (Crore)	ROE (%)
2016-17	17.49	0.03	4.53	2019 – 20	18.77	0.01	1.23
2017-18	17.66	-0.04	-7.64	2020 – 21	19.57	0.01	1.5
2018-19	18.88	0.08	1.18	2021 – 22	22.05	0.09	11.86
Mean	18.01	.02	-.64	Mean	20.13	.03	4.86

Table VII – Ratio Analysis of Management Efficiency - Bank of Baroda

Source: Authors Calculation

Table VII results show that the Merger has a positive effect on the BPE as after the merger no. of employees increased by 51.16% but the BPE shows a favourable trend as even after the increase in the number of employees BPE shows an upsurge of 2.12 Crore per employee. In FY21-22 PPE shows an upsurge as it rises to 0.09 crore. Increased BPE & PPE demonstrates improved human resource utilization. The results also state that merger has a favourable impact on the ROE as it showed an increase of 5.5%. In FY21-22 ROE is 11.86% indicating higher company profitability and indicates how effectively it generates profits after the merger. Higher ROE indicates how effectively BOB turning its equity financing into profits post-merger. (Satyanarayana, 2016) In the long run, ROE becomes essential for any bank to increase capital and, consequently, the expansion of credit.

Table VIII – Paired T-test Pre & Post Merger of Management Efficiency - Bank of Baroda

Ratios	Merger	Mean	S.D.	DF	T – Value	P – Value	Differences Pre & Post Merger
BPE	Pre	18.01	.758	2	-3.816	.062	No Significant Difference
	Post	20.13	1.710				
PPE	Pre	.02	0.060	2	-.658	.578	No Significant Difference
	Post	.03	0.046				

ROE	Pre	-.64	6.286	2	-1.244	.339	No Significant Difference
	Post	4.86	6.060				

According to the results of the paired t-test, the T-value for the BPE is -3.816 and the P-value -.062, the T-value of ROE is -.658 and P-value is .578, and the T-value of ROE is -1.244 with P-value of .339. According to the paired T-test results, the significance value is higher than the 0.05 level for BPE, PPE & ROE ratio, indicating that the merger has no significant effect on the Bank of Baroda's Management efficiency.

EARNINGS CAPABILITIES

Earnings are a measure of the bank's profitability. It evaluates the income reliability in terms of the revenue produced by core banking operations. (Karaçor, Mangir, Kodaz, & Kartal, 2017) Earnings are one of the requirements for banks to operate in a healthy manner. As a result, earnings are a crucial component of banks' profitability. (Dincer, Gencer, Orhan, & Sahinbas, 2011) Earnings ratios are inversely correlated with the likelihood of failure and positively correlated with the bank's financial performance. It includes the following ratio: -

1. Net Interest Margin

(Albulescu, 2015) The relative portion of net interest earnings with gross income is represented by the net interest margin. Because this indicator will typically be higher for banks with low leverage, it also reflects profitability. (Chen et al., 2021) It is interesting to look into how liquidity risk affects the bank performance measurements to better comprehend how it impacts banks during crises, net interest margin is used.

2. Net Profit to Average Assets

Net profit to average assets is a metric that assesses a company's profitability in relation to average assets. It can be calculated by dividing the net profit by its Average Total Assets. (Sayed & Sayed, 2013) A higher ratio indicates that the assets have a greater ability to generate income.

3. Interest Income to Total Income

(Gandhi, Chhajer, & Mehta, 2020) The ratio of interest income to total income demonstrates the contribution of interest income, which arises from the bank's core operations to total income. A higher ratio denotes, the bank's earnings from its lending operation are in a good position.

Table IX – Ratio Analysis of Earnings - Bank of Baroda
Calculation

Source:

Authors

Pre – Merger				Post – Merger			
Year	NIM (%)	NPAA (%)	IITI (%)	Year	NIM (%)	NPAA (%)	IITI (%)
2016-17	2.19	0.2024	86.19	2019 – 20	2.72	0.0563	88.04
2017-18	2.43	-0.3437	86.76	2020 – 21	2.71	0.0716	84.99
2018-19	2.72	0.0577	88.77	2021 – 22	3.03	0.5977	85.88
Mean	2.44	-.027	87.24	Mean	2.82	.241	86.30

Table IX demonstrates that, in terms of Net Interest Margin, the average pre-merger ratio was 2.44 %, while after the merger average performance increased to 2.88%. This difference of .40 bps indicates that the post-merger performance was higher than the pre-merger. It shows that bank generates high-interest margin from advances in terms of the average interest-earning paid to depositors. The results also indicate that the profitability of the bank of Baroda is not good before the merger as during FY17-18. NPAA is in negative but after the merger, it witnessed an upward trend as the NPAA ratio increased by an average of .268 indicating that the bank can generate higher profit on their assets post-merger. As per the results of Table IX, the merger has a negative effect on the Interest income as it witnessed a decline after the merger. After the merger IITI ratio continues declining, as per results it has decreased by an average of .94%. It states that a Merger doesn't have any favourable impact on Interest income.

Table X – Paired T-test Pre & Post Merger Earning Capabilities - Bank of Baroda

Ratios	Merger	Mean	S.D.	DF	T – Value	P – Value	Differences Pre & Post Merger
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NIM	Pre	2.44	.265	2	-4.737	.042	Significant Difference
	Post	2.82	.181				
NPAA	Pre	-.027	.282	2	-1.278	.329	No Significant Difference
	Post	.241	.308				
IITI	Pre	87.24	1.355	2	.655	.580	No Significant Difference
	Post	86.30	1.568				

The paired t-test results show that the T-value for the NIM is -4.737 and the P-value is .042, the T-value for the NPAA is -1.278 and the P-value is .329, and the T-value of IITI is .655 and the P-value is .580. The significance value for NPAA and IITI is higher than the 0.05 level, indicating that the merger had no significant impact on the NPAA & IITI ratio of the Bank of Baroda. While the merger has a significant impact on the Net Interest margin as its value is less than 0.05. Overall results indicate merger didn't leave any significant effect on the earning capabilities of Bank of Baroda.

LIQUIDITY

Liquidity comprehends the capacity of banks to meet their daily needs. (Kandi & Anvitha, 2022) It is extremely important for any bank to have a high level of liquidity. Otherwise, the bank may encounter several dangers that could ultimately result in insolvency. (Karaçor, Mangir, Kodaz, & Kartal, 2017) Liquid assets should be sufficient to cover short-term obligations and unforeseen cash outflows. As a result, fund management is essential for assessing banks' liquidity. (Albulescu, 2015) A trade-off between the volume of loans and the volume of liquidity may exist, even though the ability to grant loans is increased by the presence of liquidity.

It includes the following ratio: -

1. Liquid Assets to Total Deposits

To earn profits while providing liquidity to depositors, (Yadav & Jang, 2021) the bank must take the necessary measures to minimize liquidity risk by ensuring that a considerable share of assets is invested in securities with a high potential for return. The ratio of LATD shows whether there is enough liquidity available with banks for these depositors. (Roman & Sargu, 2013) The most common metrics used to gauge liquidity are the ratios of liquid assets to total assets and liquid assets to total deposits, which show how well-prepared banks are to absorb crises to cash flows.

2. Liquid Assets to Total Assets

Liquidity risk is a burden for the daily operations of banks as liquidity is required to meet the expenses of daily business operations. (Dincer, Gencer, Orhan, & Sahinbas, 2011) This demonstrates the bank's capacity to settle its debts. (Albulescu, 2015) The amount of liquidity reflects the deposit-taking bank's resilience to shocks to their balance sheets.

3. Credit Deposit Ratio

The CDR measures how much a bank is lending in comparison to the deposits accepted by the customers. Deposits are efficiently converted into loans and advances. A higher CDR denotes better deposit utilisation by the bank. (Ramchandani & Jethwani, 2017) The ratio's minimum and maximum values are not specified by RBI. However, a ratio that is too low suggests that banks are not utilising all of their resources.

Table XI – Ratio Analysis of Liquidity - Bank of Baroda

Source: Author's Calculation

Pre – Merger				Post – Merger			
Year	LATD (%)	LATA (%)	CDR (%)	Year	LATD	LATA (%)	CDR (%)
2016-17	25.01	21.65	63.69	2019 – 20	12.88	10.52	72.95
2017-18	15.71	12.90	72.28	2020 – 21	12.45	10.42	73.04
2018-19	13.97	11.45	73.40	2021 – 22	11.72	9.59	74.30

Mean	18.23	15.33	69.79	Mean	12.35	10.17	73.43
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Table XI indicates that the merger has an unfavourable effect on Liquidity as the LATD ratio shows a decline after the merger. LATD is continually declining post-merger, it shows an average decline of 5.88% indicating low liquidity over total assets which is a bad sign for its operation. (Singh & Singh, 2015) Since a bank's profitability is inversely correlated with its level of liquidity, bank profitability is thought to be dependent on fluctuations in liquidity. The results also show that the merger had a negative impact on liquidity because the LATA ratio fell as a result of the merger. Following the merger, LATD has been steadily declining; it currently shows an average decline of 5.16%, which indicates low liquidity relative to total assets - a bad sign for day-to-day operations. (Athanasoglou et al., 2008) Bank failures are primarily caused by two factors: poor asset quality and insufficient liquidity levels. Banks should focus on diversifying their portfolios and boosting their liquid assets during times of increasing uncertainty to lower their risk.

Since the CDR increased as a result of the merger, Table XI demonstrates that the merger had a favourable effect on liquidity. Following the merger, CDR has been steadily increasing; at 74.30% in FY21-22, it currently indicates high lending in relation to banks' core operations – acceptance of deposits which is favourable. BOB is able to maintain a CDR higher than the (Vaz, 2020) national average of 60 % of the banking sector.

Table XII – Paired T-test Pre & Post Merger Liquidity - Bank of Baroda

Ratios	Merger	Mean	S.D.	DF	T – Value	P – Value	Differences Pre & Post Merger
LATD	Pre	18.23	5.93	2	1.873	.202	No Significant Difference
	Post	12.35	.586				
LATA	Pre	15.33	5.51	2	1.723	.227	No Significant Difference
	Post	10.17	.510				
CDR	Pre	69.79	5.31	2	-1.295	.325	No Significant Difference
	Post	73.43	.754				

According to the results of the paired t-test, the P-value for the LATD is 1.873, the P-value is .202, LATA has a T-value of 1.723, and the P-value .227, the T-value for the CDR is -1.295 with P-value of .325, indicating that the merger had no significant effect on the Bank of Baroda's Liquidity as the significance value for LATD, LATA & CDR is higher than the 0.05 level.

CONCLUSION

This study aims to investigate the impact of the merger of Bank of Baroda with Vijaya Bank and Dena Bank on BOB's financial position post-merger. The results of the CAMEL analysis indicate that the merger doesn't have any significant impact on the financial performance of BOB. As per results out of 15 Components of the CAMEL Model, only 2 components Net NPA to Net Advances & Net Interest margin have witnessed a significant difference and the rest 13 variables didn't witness any significant difference in their ratios post-merger. Post-merger Capital adequacy of the BOB is improved as in FY21-22 CAR is 15.98 which is very high as compared to the limit prescribed by RBI of 9%. The merger is also beneficial for BOB in terms of non-performing assets as its NPA's are declining post-merger which is a good indicator, declining NPA's indicate that post-merger BOB is focusing on loan collection and non-performing asset loans were handled promptly. Findings of the study also indicate that post-merger BOB's Liquidity is declining as LATD declined by 5.88% & LATA by 5.16% as compared to an average of pre-merger results.

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